

STUDY ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS GURU BASAVA MOTORS BIDAR

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ABSTRACT

Hero motor crop Ltd. In the past hero Honda is India motor cycle and scoter produced foundation in Delhi, India Honda is being in year 1984 as shared venture among hero cycle of India and Honda Japan. The corporation is major 2-wheeler maker in India in 2006 Forbes 200 generally listing has hero Honda motor ranked at 108. In 2010 When Honda settle on to move out sine the combine course hero group obtain the shares alleged by Honda after in August 2011 the company was renamed hero motor crop with fresh co corporate character. On 4th June 2012 Hero motors crop accept a proper to amalgamate the invited arm of its parent Hero Investment Pvt. Ltd Into the automaker. The conclusion arrive after 19 months slip from Honda motor. The branch personality and symbol of hero motors crop by the London firm Wolff Olin The logo was exposed on 9th August 2011 in London the day before third test match between India.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The project is founded on analyzing consumer approval with Hero motor crop Ltd. In recent year companies. The weight is how to keep customer. It is trouble free to focus for fresh client and the keep customer old patrons. Therefore company are tough to center this of satisfaction. The work of this project was carrier out to locate away if a client in happy or unhappy moreover to determine the point of customer pleasure and offer this reaction to company. The initial chapter of the task involves gathering information from client to interpret the characteristic according to whom the buyer sense satisfied or dissatisfied.

1.2 INDUSTRI PROFILE

The Indian two wheeler vehicle bring the higher volume among all other subdivision of automotive diligences . The two wheeler vehicle is very divers motor vehicle devise to outfit a different purpose optio. The displacement to the instance of the moments like union a motor cycle and union attending a motorcycle is a connected social Hildebrand and Wolfmuller become the initial motor cycle of the production of sequence and will be called motors. In 2014,3 best motorcycle produced in world for an amount were Honda, Yamaha ,both are Hero JAPAN motor Ltd (INDIA)

India is the subsequent biggest product of 2 wheeler segment of 2 wheeler contribute the main volume among all segment in the automotive commerce. The industry is rising to 30%

each year sell 2 wheeler vehicle in the 2008-09 period was 785.7548 Which was an advance of 12% The Indian 2wheeler industry is the 54 year old Bajaj automobile being product

1.3 COMPANY PROFILE

Hero motor crop Ltd(previous Hero Honda motor Ltd) is the planet biggest 2wheeler produce base in India ,in 2000 the company achievement desire place of individual the major 2wheeler built corporation in India and also the “number 1 in the world “ in 2011 headquartered in new Delhi India and continue on the way to grip this position to date.

In the present day each install bicycle sell the domination is hero bike . each 30 second somebody in India buy the best selling hero bike

Hero motor crop has 3 development vegetation based in dharuhera Gurgaon in Haryana and Haridwar in Uttarakhand . together preserve make 3 million bicycle a year more then 3100 dealer through India hero Honda have a buyer faithfully course from the time when 2000 the hero Honda permit series.

The company believed it have return of 12 billion a capacity of 12 million 2wheeler for 2017-18 along through the fresh country wheeler they can nowadays market there 2wheeler after Honda hero motor crop plane to get 10% of its profit world market and plan to start sale in Nigeria between

2.1 THEOROTICAL BACKGROUND OF CUSTOMER PERCEPTION

CUSTOMER PERCEPTION

Perception is the process by which the information from environment is college organization received and interpreted to do it meaning full for us. And also the perception is the method by which people were manage recognize their impression to make meaning to the environment.

DEFINATION

Perception is the all about the process by which the individual know the information about environment feeling, smelling, tasting and hearing

DENAMINATION OF PERCEPTION

Perception consist of the a few sub process . To recognize the dynamic of the perceptual process one can take input throught ,and the resulting opinion approach, attitude etc, these all factor were influence on our performance can be view as perception

Element of the perception:

Elements of perception are divided into two groups

(a) absolute threshold

a) absolute threshold

The absolute threshold is the lowest stage of stimulus intensity required for a motivation to perceive. The absolute threshold is the value of the intensity required to detect a difference between nothing and something. For example, you are driving on the road and a billboard is on the road in the distance. And on the entertaining ever copy writing but the print is very small so that's why it is not possible to see from the road. Absolute threshold is that point you first see the billboard and is not sufficient to see. So the absolute threshold is the customer did not see or hear that properly so the customer will not be activated and the stimuli not be consciously perceived.

b) differential threshold The negligible difference so as can be noticed among two similar stimuli is known as differential threshold.

This concept was developed by German scientist named Ernst Weber in the 19th century. He observed that the just noticeable difference of the intensity of the first stimuli at stimuli. According to the Weber law for instance if the price of a color T.V increasing by Rs.100/. The increase in price may not be noticed. But if the domestic cooking gas price increasing even by one, this will easily be noticed by consumer. This is the case of cooking gas this price increasing is a signification of the basic cost of the cooking gas and the consumer attention will be drawn to the price high.

Weber law has very good marketing application. Marketers are using Weber's law to determine the relevant just noticeable difference for various reasons. In the case of reduction made in production size increasing in product price and reduced quality the firm would not want the public to notice the difference without being wastefully extravagant. For instance because of increasing cost, firm have to choose between increasing price and reduce the quality offered at the existent price. But marketing have preferred to keep itself in the consideration set of the consumer mind by making a change in quality. For instance Maruthi Udyog Ltd. was forced to reduce the price of its Maruthi 800, Zen and other just before India was launching in the market.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW:

The 2-wheeler is the going has development always but the to slow down. The impact was really felt in subsequent year when large growth was only 2% mopeds to have a capacity of around 21% planning the future to reach the long term aim is much needed to survival and growth of all business change the today strategic planning must take into the rapid technology change the increasing in spirited and the turbulent business

India has the leading no of 2-wheeler vehicle in world with 42.7 million vehicle 40% of cars 72% 2-wheelr vehicle hero was founded on april 13 1984 the India 2-wheelre production can be generally classify

Cocotte, woodruff and jenkiss(1987)

Customer perception “conceptual as a feeling develops valuation of experience”

Philip kotler(2013)

Customer perception is predetermined based upon customer perception

Armstrong(2011):

Customer perception is sophisticated word, which is made up of broad diversity of factor”

Brown:

“The state which product or service of need desire and expectation of the client are satisfied to overcome the outcome in repetition of purchase and favorable value of themouth”

Jones and sasser

The basic element of the customer perception are product or service basic support service a recovery process to counter negative experience and extraordinary service

Oliver(1997):

Perception is the adjustment of consumer that product recommended pleasure compliance levels related to consumer

Marsha pater(2014)

The examiner changes in the after purchase production perception for the goods purchase the perception is considered in a cross- sectional and longitudinal study of bike owner most of the customer with high product participation show the great perception with comparing

James thong(2007):

The study helps to the post adoption beliefs on the expectation the conformation the model for the advancing technology. And the information technology in developing day by day with new technology adoption

Marshal richins 2003

The ownership post usage perception is making effect on the involvement of strong commodities purchase.

Contribution and perception variable were calculated in cross section and a longitudinal study about the bike user the perception the costly bike user show slightly better perception of the low customer over the term of ownership

3.RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The survey help to know the customer perception about the sale service of the hero motor crop. The study helps that to collected the information about customer feedback or opinion of the hero motor. The study cover the customer hero motor in Bidar. The study helps to the company to examine the level of customer satisfaction. The study assist the business to development the customer perception result considering of all the question of analyzing the customer perception result.

3.2 NEEDFOR THE STUDY

Hero motor crop have a reputed service in the market , and the company a hug range of operation and excellent service for the customer once comparing to its competition, due to this it lagged behind in the competition with bike service providers.

3.3 OBJECTVES OF THE STUDY

To know customer awareness level regarding total number of free service offered by guru basava motors

To study customer perception towards guru basava motors

To study which factor influence on customer while giving their vehicle for servicing

To know customer satisfaction towards after sales servicing

To study customer opinion regarding behavior of the staff during service.

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The survey help to know the customer perception about the sales servicing of the hero motor crop

The study assister the business to develop their promotion activities.

The study covers the customer of hero motor in mannakhelli.

The study help to the company to examination the level of customer satisfaction.

The study helps that collect the information about the feedback or opinion of the hero

4. DATA ANAYSIS AND INTREPETATION

4.1 DO YOU HAVE OWN HERO BIKE?

SI No	Particular	No Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	25	50%
2	No	25	50%
	Total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

From the above the graph it was founded that respondents have own hero motor bike respondents yes is 50% and no is 50%

4.2 TABLE SHOWING THE RESPONDETS WHICH MODEL HAVE THE MOTOR CYCLE

SL NO	PARTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Splendore 100	12	24
2	Glamour 125	16	32
3	Karizma150	15	30
4	Splendore pro	7	14
	Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above the graph it was model 1) splendore plus100 24% 2)glamour 125 32% 3)karizma 150 30% 4) splendore pro 14%

4.3COME FOR SERVICE WITH APPOINTMENT

Sl. N0	Particulore	Respondent	Parcentage
1	Without Appointment	10	20%
2	With Appointment	40	80%
	Total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION

From the graph it was found that maximum respondent are aware the total no of service by the guru basava motors 1)no46% 2)yes56%

4.5 Dealer Is Provided 3 Time Free Services Or Not:

SL. NO	PARTICULORE	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	No	17	34%
2	Yes	33	66%
	Total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

From the above graph it was founded the most respondent ask that dealer is the providing 3 times free service for the customer 1)no 34% 2)yes66%

4.6 CO-OPRATION OF THE STAFF DURING SERVICE:

SL. NO	CO-OPRATION	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	Excellent	7	14%
2	Fair	5	10%
3	Good	26	52%
4	Bad	4	8%
5	Very Bad	8	16%
	Total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

From the above graph will be shows the staff behavior while interacting with the customer is the very co- operative of the staff 1)excellent 14%2)fair10%3)good52%4)bad8%5)very bad16%

4.7DELIVERY OF THE VEHICALE ON TIME:

SL.NO	PARTICULORE	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	Yes	21	42%
2	No	29	58%
	TOTAL	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

the above graph shows that guru basava motors following in the time delivery system
1)yes42%2)no58%

4.8 DURING SERVICE ALL COMPLAINTS WERE ADDRESSED PROPERLY:

Sl. No	particulore	respondent	Percentage
1	yes	38	76%
2	No	12	24%
	total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

from the above it was found that most of the respondent are satisfied with respect to address that problem or complain 1)yes 76% 2)no24%

4.9 Factors Consider Most While Giving Vehicle For Service:

SL.NO	PARTICULORE	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	Good Service	17	34%
2	Staff Behaviore	22	44%
3	Availablity Of Spare Parts	5	10%
4	Timely Delivery	2	4%
5	Other	4	8%
	Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION:

from the above graph it was found that most of the respondent consider good service while giving their bike servicing 1)good service34%2)staff behavioure44%3)availability of the spare part 10%4)timely delivery 4% 5)other 8%

4.10 What are those suggestion to improve quality of service at guru basava motors

SL.NO	PARTICULORE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	After Sales A Service	22	44%
2	Staff Attitude	12	24%
3	Pre Sales Service	16	32%
	Total	50	100%

INTERPRETATION:

From the above graph searched many customer are ready give future paid service at guru basava motor 1)after sales a service 44%

4.11 Satisfy Of The After Sales Service Provided At

SL.NO	PARTICULORE	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	Completely Satisfied	3	6%
2	Fair	29	58%
3	Satisfied	6	12%
4	Dis Satisfied	9	18%
5	Completely Dis Satisfied	3	6%
	Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above the graph it was found that respondent satisfied with the after sales service provided 1)completely satisfied 6% 2)fair 58%3)satisfies 12%4)dis satisfied 18% 5)completely dis satisfied 6%

4.12 How they providing service of your bike at guru basava motor mannakhelli

Sl. No	Particulore	Respondent	Percentage
1	Cheap	14	28%
2	Costly	18	36%
3	Moderate	18	36%
	Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above that graph will be show that large number of the respondent feels the cost paid service is moderate 1)cheap 28% 2)costly 36% 3) moderate 36%

5.1 FINDINGS

1. from the survey it was found that most of the respondent are aware total number of the free service providing by the guru basava motors.
2. maximum number of the hero splendore use are satisfied with respect to addressing their complaint. This indicate that guru basava motor crop has giving care on solving costomer problem.
3. from this survey it was they also found that most of the respondent are ready to giving future paid service at guru basava motor crop
4. the most of the customer are satisfied with the after sales of the guru basava motor.
5. from this survey it was found that large number of the respondent feels that cost of paid service is moderate.
6. guru basava motors dealer providing 6 time free service for the customer .
7. the most respondent are consider are good service while giving their bike for servicing.
8. they staff behavior while interacting with the customer is very co operative.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS:

Some of the respondent is unaware of the total number of the service which guru Basava motors crop are providing. So it is suggestion that guru basava motor service station they should stick a pamphlet or hoarding which gives information about the service .

Some of the respondent completely satisfied after sales service provided at guru basava motor crop. So it is suggest that in guru basava motor provide the best service at the to all paid service.

Guru basava motors have to the to giving preference for those who have come for service without appointed.

Minimum number of the respondent not preferring future paid service at guru basava motor crop. So it is the suggestion of that service to providing all respondent will prefer the future paid serviced .

Maximum number of the respondent believe that the paid service at guru basava motor crop is modern of the and nearly half of the them don't want to giving their bike for paid service because they did not find any difference between local garages and in the service of that station. So is suggestion them to giving advertisement with regard to paid service

6.CONCLUSIONS:

We can conclusion that the hero motor user are young and generation and the middle age personal are interest in the bike design and respect for the iconic trademark from the survey it was found that the most number of the user are satisfy with the service provide by the company and also the most number user are feeling good about the after sales service provide by the company. Hero splendore bike attraction the customer with the new model and the bike power. From this survey it was founded that overall performance of the guru basava motors is good. And maximum number of the customer are satisfied with their after sales service.

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